

User Testing of AI-Assisted Mapping Tool fAIr

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This abstract was accepted to the OSMScience 2025 Conference after peer-review.

Humanitarian organizations need maps for their activities. However, there is a lack of quality maps in many countries. The Humanitarian OpenStreetMap Team (HOT) is coordinating a global effort for humanitarian mapping, where volunteers create maps of remote localities. They use satellite imagery to search for roads and buildings and draw them into the OpenStreetMap. Despite all the efforts of volunteers, many regions remain insufficiently mapped [1]. Artificial intelligence (AI) is already used to analyze satellite imagery. There is thus an opportunity to use AI for humanitarian mapping as well. HOT proposed the fAIr project (<https://fair.hotosm.org/>) – an open-source AI-assisted mapping tool [2]. In a presentation from SOTM 2024, Anna Zanchetta [3] analyzed the performance of fAIr in detecting buildings in different conditions.

Our group, located in the Department of Geography, Faculty of Science, Masaryk University, Czechia, is part of the humanitarian mapping community Missing Maps Czechia and Slovakia. We were in contact with the fAIr developers from HOT – Omran Najjar, Kshitij Sharma, and Anna Zanchetta. They asked us if we could organize user testing of the first version of fAIr. The goal was to compare AI-assisted mapping of buildings with the fAIr tool and classic manual mapping of buildings without AI assistance. The popular JOSM editor, which offers experienced tools for manual building mapping, was used for comparison.

The experiment took place in an online environment during November 2024. The experiment took place in four different sessions, so each participant could choose the day and time that suited them best. Training datasets were prepared for 24 different localities around the globe. The localities were divided into easy (14) and complex (10). Complex localities were characterized by a high density of buildings and poorer imagery quality. 26 participants took part in the experiment – 14 beginners and 12 experienced contributors (with more than 1000 buildings in OpenStreetMap mapped). The participants were divided into groups A and B, so there were similar numbers of experienced contributors and beginners in both groups.

Each participant was assigned one locality to map in fAIr and one locality to map in JOSM. One of the localities was easy and the other complex, so that a similar number of easy and complex localities were mapped in each editor. It was also ensured that beginners and experienced contributors mapped a similar number of easy and complex localities in both editors. The selection of a locality from easy localities and the selection of a locality from complex localities were random. It was possible for two participants to map the same complex locality because there were fewer of them. This did not affect the results, because the participants did not see each other's data.

Štampach, R., Fila, M., Horák, J., & Krotíl, H. (2026). User testing of AI-assisted mapping tool fAIr
In: M. Minghini, S. Martinez, B. P. V. Samson, A. Zanchetta, P. Mooney, & A. Y. Grinberger (Eds.) Proceedings of OSM Science 2025.
Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.21008440>

Each session was structured as follows:

- An explanation of the rules for correctly and incorrectly mapped buildings.
- 45 minutes: group A mapped in fAIr, group B mapped in JOSM
- 5 minutes: break
- 45 minutes: group B mapped in fAIr, group A mapped in JOSM
- Participants filled in the feedback questionnaire.

Validators evaluated the mapped buildings, and the results were analyzed. Efficiency (number of buildings mapped per minute), effectiveness (proportion of buildings mapped correctly), and satisfaction (feedback from participants) were analyzed. Mapping in JOSM (86.08 %) was significantly more accurate and faster (4.23 buildings/min) than the fAIr tool (78.22 % and 1.97 buildings/min).

Beginners mapped faster in JOSM (2.89 buildings/min) than in fAIr (2.08 buildings/min), but the mapping quality was almost the same in JOSM (79.28 %) and fAIr (80.41 %). Experienced contributors mapped much faster (5.69 buildings/min) and with higher quality (93.45 %) in JOSM than in fAIr (1.84 buildings/min and 75.38 %). Interestingly, it also means that beginners have better results of mapping quality (80.41%) and mapping speed in fAIr (2.08 buildings/min) than experienced contributors (75.38 % and 1.84 buildings/min). On the contrary, experienced contributors have much better results in mapping quality (93.45 %) and mapping speed (5.69 buildings/min) in JOSM than beginners (79.28 % and 2.89 buildings/min).

We also analyzed the influence of the complexity of mapping locality, e.g., the density of buildings in the mapped site and the quality of the imagery. For easy localities, experienced contributors generally have higher mapped building counts, indicating better fAIr performance on simpler tasks. For complex localities, the number of buildings mapped by experienced contributors drops significantly, suggesting that complex localities pose a challenge even for experienced contributors. A higher number of errors was found in complex localities, where AI likely generated lower-quality building outlines. Interestingly, for complex localities, beginners mapped more buildings than experienced contributors, which may suggest that they focus on quantity. This could indicate potential quality issues.

An example of data can be seen in Figure 1. In the JOSM editor, participants mapped building by building. In fAIr, buildings are mapped at larger distances. The reason is that participants selected only those buildings for which the AI model generated a high-quality outline, which is the correct procedure. In the case of fAIr, participants mapped practically only buildings with a simple shape. For buildings with a more complex shape, fAIr apparently failed to create a high-quality outline successfully.

Figure 1. Buildings mapped using the fAIr tool (green) and the JOSM editor (blue).

23 participants answered a mapping feedback questionnaire. They indicated that fAIr was not their preferred tool for mapping, but more than half of them said they would return to it. In their opinion, fAIr is suitable for beginners. Most participants stated that the buildings generated by AI need to be further modified and that correcting errors is difficult.

After evaluating the results and feedback from participants, recommendations were proposed for the further development of the fAIr tool:

- fAIr is a beginner-friendly tool. It is suitable for quick mapping of simple features. Users appreciated the simple interface. Beginners have similar results in fAIr as experienced contributors, sometimes even better. Users suggested combining both tools – starting with quick mapping in fAIr and refining the quality in JOSM.
- Participants had issues with AI-generated shapes, as fAIr did not allow proper mapping of more complex buildings. Often, separate buildings were mistakenly combined into a single outline. These problems were greater in the complex areas (e.g., density of the mapped site and the quality of the imagery), where the AI seemed unable to design good building outlines.
- The results were influenced by the fact that JOSM includes tools for mapping buildings, which gives it an advantage over fAIr. However, JOSM does not have specialized tools for mapping other features (e.g., roads). It is possible that mapping these features would yield more favorable results for fAIr.
- Users believe that fAIr has the potential to improve the mapping process and could be helpful if key problems are addressed.

Some problems will likely be solved using innovations in the new version of fAIr – e.g., using a YOLO-type ML model and increasing the speed of prediction of building outlines [2]. A logical continuation of our study would be to repeat user testing with the new version of fAIr – e.g., compare the results of the RAMP model from the original version of fAIr with the YOLO model from the latest version in the same locality. We want to not only scientifically test the new version of fAIr, but also use it during the autumn at one of the mapathons we organize in the Missing Maps Czechia and Slovakia. Ideally, fAIr would be used at a mapathon that will be attended mainly by contributors with experience in using AI, e.g., employees of IT companies.

The results of the experiment were published as a public scientific report [4]: <https://drive.google.com/file/d/10I1wz1BHsBXmBjXMx99KzqBwaVpj5MJN/view?usp=sharing>.

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